

**LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND PRACTICES OF BIDS AND AWARDS
COMMITTEE TOWARDS GOVERNMENT PROCUREMENT
REFORM ACT (RA9184)**

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Level of Awareness and Practices of Bids and Awards Committee Towards Government Procurement Reform Act (RA9184)

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Abstract

This study determined the level of awareness and practices of the 102 BAC members towards the Government Procurement Reform Act of schools in North II District in the Division of Iligan City. The study was conducted in the second quarter of the school year 2022-2023. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to test the significant relationship between the respondents' procurement practices, demographic profile, and level of awareness; and which variable best predicts the dependent variable. The study utilized a researcher-made instrument in gathering the data. Most of the respondents were 33 to 41 years old, female, married, with a bachelor's degree, had rendered services for 2 – 5 years, and had attended less than two seminars/ trainings. In the respondents' level of awareness in terms of MOOE procurement process, the result showed that the respondents were "Very aware" in the procurement process. In terms of the practices of the respondents in the utilization, the respondents also went on Shopping as their mode of procurement. On the other hand, the practices in terms of procurement processes interpreted as being practiced. Furthermore, in regression analysis, the respondents' procurement practices in utilization were affected by the level of awareness. The null hypothesis stated that there was no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' procurement practices in utilization was rejected.

Keywords: *level of awareness and practices, procurement practices, and processes procurement law (9184) government procurement reform act*

Introduction

The development of a sound educational program is a major concern of school administration. The success of this program largely depends on the services and support given by the Department of Education through allocations of schools on the release of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses or MOOE. The use of MOOE is based on general guidelines on government procurement acts which is hard to follow due to lack of knowledge and skills in certain mode of procurement and its corresponding procedure.

Good governance and regulatory management are essential to regulatory reform because they are important catalysts between reform objectives and reform results. Good governance is inherently linked to economic and social reforms. If government capacities to produce, co-ordinate, implement and review regulatory reform are not in place, there is a high risk that economic or social reforms will be inefficient or fail. The quality of the instruments and institutions of regulation are a defining element of effective governance and of regulatory reform capacities.

In schools were teachers serving also as Bids and awards Committee (BAC) member, tends to spend less time during the convene period wherein school needs were not properly addressed. The procurement of goods, and/ or services then relies mostly on the accessibility and promptness of the supplier. The conveniency on the part of the buyer is also observed because of the allotted period in submitting the liquidation reports is timely. In case of delay, the school will not be given a chance to be downloaded for the succeeding funds. If worsen, the school head will be reprimanded through answering the demand letter/ order and that would affect the performance of the whole school which form part of the Performance Bonus given to teachers.

The government procurement system is decentralized, where responsibility and control rests with each agency. It is perceived to be cumbersome, fragmented and inefficient process with many loopholes that are prone to corruption. There are issues on waste, inefficiency, lack of transparency, widespread corruption, low levels of capacity, and the absence of accountability in public procurement which greatly affects public administration, resulting to poorly resourced public services and under-developed infrastructure. Despite the so-called world class regulation and recent developments, public procurement in the Philippines never escapes scandals and controversies.

The Department of Education Order 49, series 2001 that is creating the Bids and Awards Committee (BAC) for the Department of Education. This is to facilitate the implementation of various projects of the department. It states that the BAC shall be responsible for eligibility screening, bidding, evaluation of bids, post-qualification and recommending awards of contrasts. It also states for Two private sector representatives (non-voting), One Private sector representative shall be chosen from the ranks of professional groups such as PICPA, ACPAP, GACPA, ACPAE, Philippine Contractors Association and others. The other private sector representative shall be chosen from the end-user/NGO. The BAC shall have a permanent Secretariat headed by a Director who shall be assisted by at least two (2) technical assistants, secretaries, a clerk and a messenger. All existing Orders/Memoranda that are inconsistent with this Order are hereby repealed.

Specifically, the Bids and Awards Committee (BAC) shall be responsible for ensuring compliance with the standards in the law in the

procurement of goods and services and prosecuting infrastructure projects of the agency. Every school manager/administrator as well as the BAC members must be knowledgeable on school planning financial aspect of planning and other related issues. He/she must be able to identify current challenges to school finance, i.e., voucher plans, MOOE's, etc. Aside from this, knowledge on school purchasing procedures/issues including the function, purpose and process of bidding, requests for proposals and qualifications, etc. is imperative. Learning and management skill about managing school facilities, including internal controls, handling of cash, bank accounts, reconciliations, and other issues and processes needed.

To avoid such similar problems and to standardize the release to the implementation of the school Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE's), the Department of Education released DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2014 Implementing Guidelines on the Direct Release of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE's) allocations of schools to the respective implementing units. The Department of Budget and Management (DBM) and DepEd Joint Circular no. 2004-1 dated January 1, entitled "Guidelines on the Direct Release of Funds to DepEd Regional Offices and Implementing Units." This law guides the school heads on the management, operation, and control of the financial operations at the school level. The BAC members will also be vigilant with the mandates in the procurement procedure.

The main objective of the study was to determine the level of awareness and practices of BAC members towards Government Procurement Reform Act of schools in North II District in Iligan City division. The study was conducted on the second quarter of school year 2022-2023. The researcher is a business administration graduate and a teacher by profession. She is on five years of service as disbursing officer at Sultan Mamarinta Panandigan Integrated School, Bonbonon, Iligan City. Preparing liquidation reports on the quarterly downloading of budget on Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) of school equipped her in acquiring completeness on reports. Also, the researcher wanted to contribute timeliness and accurateness by following guidelines imposed by Commission on Audit as well as to the educational system.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of awareness and practices of Bids and Awards Committee members (teachers) towards Government Procurement Reform Act of the schools under North II District in Iligan City during the SY 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational qualification;
 - 1.5. length of services; and
 - 1.6. number of seminars attended on RA 9184 (Government Reform Procurement Act)?
2. What is the level of awareness of the respondents in terms of MOOE procurement process?
3. What are the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses in terms of;
 - 3.1. procurement practices in utilization, and
 - 3.2. procurement processes?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the level of awareness in procurement process?
6. Which of the demographic profile and level of awareness best predict practices in the utilization of the MOOE of the respondents?
7. What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research was used in describing the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service and seminars attended; the knowledge and practices of BAC members towards Government Procurement Reform Act. It was also correlation research since the procurement practices of the respondents were correlated to the level of awareness and their demographic profile.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Elementary and Secondary School Bids and Award Committee members (teachers) of North II District in Iligan City Division during the school year 2022-2023. Complete enumeration was used in the study which summed up to 102 teachers.

Table 1. *Number of Respondents per School*

No	Schools	No. of BAC members		
		Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
1.	Sta. Felomina Central School	1	5	6 (5.88)
2.	Kiwalan Elementary School	1	6	7 (6.86)
3.	Acmac Elementary School	3	2	5 (4.90)
4.	Echavez Elementary School	0	5	5 (4.90)
5.	Sultan Mamarinta Panandigan Integrated School	1	7	8 (7.84)
6.	Benito S. Ong Elementary School	0	6	6 (5.88)
7.	Venancio Siarza Memorial Elementary School	0	6	6 (5.88)
8.	Sardab Elementary School	1	4	5 (4.90)
9.	Ampucao Elementary School	3	3	6 (5.88)
10.	Mainit Elementary School	1	4	5 (4.90)
11.	Lower Mainit Elementary School	1	4	5 (4.90)
12.	Rebucon Elementary School	0	5	5 (4.90)
13.	Pudog Elementary School	1	4	5 (4.90)
14.	Caribao Elementary School	0	5	5 (4.90)
15.	Kapisahan Elementary School	1	3	4 (3.92)
16.	Iligan City East High School- Sta. Felomina	0	7	7 (6.86)
17.	Kiwalan National High School	1	6	7 (6.86)
18.	Mainit High School	1	4	5 (4.90)
Total		16 (15.68%)	86 (84.31%)	102 (100%)

Instruments

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire based in the Government Procurement Reform Act (RA9184) in gathering the data which underwent validation through pilot testing and checking by experts. The survey instrument was composed of 25 items and answered by checking the corresponding number based on the procurement practices and the level of awareness regarding the Government Procurement Reform Act (RA9184). The first part dealt with the demographic profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and number of seminars attended. The second part was the level of awareness in procurement process composed of 8 statements.

Likewise, the third part dealt with the procurement practices on MOOE utilization in terms of procurement practices in utilization and procurement processes composed of 17 indicators. The Likert-scale was used and measured using 4-point scale ranging from 1-not aware, 2-less aware, 3-aware, and 4- very aware for the level of awareness. For procurement practices in utilization, 1-Never, 2-Sometimes, 3-Often, and 4- Always, while for the procurement processes, 1-not practiced at all, 2-less practiced, 3-practiced, and 4-highly practiced.

The instrument had a pilot testing at Pedro Baculio Elementary School, Kibonbon Elementary School, Ulaliman Elementary School, Himaya Elementary School, Sambulawan Elementary School, Sambulawan National High School, and San Francisco de Asia National High School, Division of El Salvador City.

Table 2. *Reliability Analysis of Variables*

Variables	Number of Questions	Cronbach Alpha	Interpretation
Level of awareness	8	0.726	Reliable
Procurement practices on MOOE utilization			
Procurement practices	7	0.717	Reliable
Procurement processes	10	0.751	Reliable

Table 2 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result shows that the questionnaire consisted of 25 questions composed of the level of awareness with a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.726; procurement practices with 0.717; and the procurement processes with 0.751, which indicated that all questions were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents understood the research questions, and similar questions are answered in the same direction.

Procedure

The researcher personally conducted the study and facilitated the gathering of data. The data gathering process was done in this manner.

A letter was made subjected for approval from Dean of Graduate Studies to allow her to conduct the study among BAC members of North II District in Division of Iligan City. When approved, the researcher collected contact details to reach out to the respondents to request to be part of the study. After given permission, the researcher explained the purpose of the study to all respondents. The researcher collected the data by means of survey questionnaire. After the respondents answered the survey questionnaire; it was checked, tallied, interpreted and analyzed based from the problems cited in the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were employed to answer the different problems presented in Chapter 1 using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS):

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used in analyzing the profile of teachers as to age, sex, civil status, highest educational qualification, length of services, and number of seminars attended on RA 9184 (Government Reform Procurement Act).

For problems 2 and 3, Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the level of awareness and practices of the BAC members (teachers) with regards to mode and process of procurement.

For problem 4, Chi-square Test was used to determine significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile.

For problem 5, Pearson's R Correlation was used to test the significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the level of awareness in procurement process.

For problem 6, Regression was used to determine in which of the demographic profile, level of awareness, and practices best predict practices in the utilization of the MOOE of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational qualification, length of services, and number of seminars attended on RA 9184 (Government Reform Procurement Act)?

Table 3. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in Years Old)</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
25 – 32	34	33.3
33 – 41	42	41.2
42 – 49	19	18.6
50 – 57	6	5.9
58 – 65	1	1.0
Total	102	100.0

Table 3 presents the age of the respondents. The result showed that teachers having the age of 33 to 41 years of age had the highest percentage of 41.2 %. This implied that most of the respondent's teachers where in their young adulthood to nearly Middle adulthood. This is supported by Gray (2006) stated that it is on this stage of life that people are most focus on the career or job financial stability and achievement.

Table 4. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	14	13.7
Female	88	86.3
Total	102	100.0

Table 4 displays the sex of the respondents. The result presented that number of females outnumbered the number of males. This implies that 86.3 % of female teachers in the North II District were BAC members knowing that teaching was mostly a chosen career for females. There has been an ideological link between women's domestic role and their career as school teacher. Teaching is important and it is a well-regarded profession within our community and people from all walks of life find it as a professionally and personally gives satisfaction as a career choice.

There were a lot of qualities of a good teacher that include skills in communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, empathy and patience. She focuses on collaboration that is working in education means you're never truly working alone. From paraprofessionals and teaching assistants to other classroom teachers and school leaders, working as a teacher often means working effectively in a group. It's also important to keep an open mind and learn from other educators. (Gagnon, 2019)

Table 5. *Civil Status of the Respondents*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Single	14	13.7
Married	88	86.3
Total	102	100.0

Table 5 displays the civil status of the respondents. The result presented that 86.3% (88) of the respondents are married BAC members and 13.7 % (13.7) of the respondents are single in the time of administering the questionnaires. There is a big difference on the marital status of the respondents.

Knowing that married people are both responsible for and responsible to another human being, and both halves of that dynamic lead the married to live more responsible, fruitful, and satisfying lives. It is a transformative act, that is changing the way two people look at each other, at the future, and at their roles in society (Gottman, 2019)

Table 6. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor’s Degree	81	79.4
With Master’s Unit	19	18.6
Master’s Degree	1	1.0
Doctoral Degree	1	1.0
Total	102	100.0

Table 6 displays the highest educational attainment of the respondents. The result presented 79.4 % (81) of the respondents earned a bachelor’s degree, 18.6 % (19) are in Post Graduate with earned units, and 1% (1) for both Master’s and Doctoral degree. The result implies that most of the respondents graduated with a bachelor’s degree. As cited in DepEd order 19, series 2016 on Hiring and Appointment of teaching staff in public schools, qualified teachers must have earned a bachelor’s degree as Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education (BEED) or Bachelor of Science in Education (BSE) units.

Table 7. *Length of Service of the Respondents*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1 year and below	21	20.6
2 – 5 years	41	40.2
6 – 10 years	17	16.7
11 – 14 years	12	11.8
15 years and above	11	10.8
Total	102	100.0

Table 7 shows the respondents’ length of service. The result revealed that 40.2 % (41) of the respondents had served the institution from 2 to 5 years and 10.8% (11) had served 15 years above. This implies that a BAC member as chosen by the Head of Procuring Entity (HoPE) rendered services for at least 5 years to be able him to participate in the procurement process.

Workers possess varying levels of skills and abilities, and a performance-based promotion rewards those who may have the most to offer the organization in the long run. While tenured employees offer the benefit of greater experience, this does not necessarily equate with more ability if their skills no longer match the needs of an evolving organization (Thompson, 2019).

Table 8. *Respondents’ Number of Trainings/Seminars Attended*

<i>Number of Trainings/Seminars Attended</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
None	37	36.3
Less than 2 seminars/training	57	55.9
6-8 seminars/training	6	5.9
More than 11 seminars/training	2	2.0
Total	102	100.0

Table 8 displays the respondents’ number of trainings/seminars attended. The result presented that 55.9 % (57) of the respondents have attended less than 2 seminars/ trainings. While only 2 (2%) respondents attended more than 11 seminars.

It implies that respondents cannot easily joined seminars/trainings because they had classes to be taken care of. Nevertheless, instructed and advised by the school head to attend to and there was certain memorandum that limits the participants in attending the seminars per school as cited in Division Memorandum for trainings.

As much as professional development opportunities may be more difficult because they generally require money. Most small organizations simply don’t have the resources to pay for staff members’ college or graduate courses and may not even be able to afford conference fees. While some staff members may be more than willing to pay for their own conferences or courses, it would be unfair to require everyone to do so. A compromise might be to ask staff members to take advantage of at least one professional development opportunity per year. Such training opportunities could be as low-key as a half-hour presentation at a staff meeting, or as formal as a

presentation or workshop by a nationally known expert in the field, depending upon the organization's resources (Community Toolbox,2023).

The importance of high-quality training is crucial because the cost to the organization is often significant. The cost of training includes the training course itself, travel expenses, and lost hours from work to attend training. (Borges,2023)

Problem 2: What is the level of awareness of the respondents in terms of MOOE procurement process?

Table 9. Level of Awareness of the Respondents in terms of MOOE procurement process

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Preparation of the Annual Procurement Plan (APP) and PPMP as basis for procurement.	3.45	±	0.59	Very Aware
2. Preparation of the Bidding documents by the BAC Secretariat	3.26	±	0.50	Very Aware
3. Advertisement and Posting of the Invitation to Bid- to newspapers of general circulation shall not be required for contracts to bid with an approved budget of PhP2Million and below for the procurement of goods: and PhP5Million and below for infrastructure projects.	2.18	±	0.95	Less Aware
4. Post qualification of Bids to determine whether the bid submitted by the bidder with the Lowest Calculated is responsive.	2.80	±	1.20	Aware
5. Issuance of the BAC Resolution Recommending the Award of the Contract with the bidder with the Lowest Calculated Responsive Bid	3.28	±	0.53	Very Aware
6. Issuance of Notice to Award.	3.41	±	0.49	Very Aware
7. Signing of Contract or Purchase Order.	3.45	±	0.50	Very Aware
8. Issuance of notice to proceed.	3.29	±	0.61	Very Aware
Weighted Mean	3.14	±	0.47	Aware

Note: 3.25-4.00 - Very Aware; 2.50-3.24 - Aware; 1.75-2.49 - Less Aware; 1.00-1.74 - Not Aware

Table 9 below presents the level of awareness of the respondents in terms of MOOE procurement process. The result showed with a mean of 3.45 the respondents are “very aware” in the procurement process that starts with the preparation of the Annual Procurement Plan (APP) and PPMP as basis for procurement, a mean of preparation of the bidding documents by the BAC Secretariat, the issuance of the BAC resolution recommending the award of the contract with the bidder with the lowest calculated responsive Bid, the issuance of notice to award, signing of contract or purchase order and the issuance of notice to proceed. They were “less aware” in Advertisement and Posting of the Invitation to Bid- to newspapers of general circulation shall not be required for contracts to bid with an approved budget of PhP2Million and below for the procurement of goods: and PhP5Million and below for infrastructure projects.

This simply implies that with a mean of 3.14, the respondents are “aware “of the procurement process and that not all procurement procedure are to be followed because they differ in required documents needed in the procuring of goods and services for the school as cited in General Guidelines in the Procurement for School (RA 9184). The respondents were “less aware” with the number 3 procurement process because budget funds for MOOE was not allowable to spend exceeding Php 50,000.00 worth of goods and/or services. Hence, no advertisement and posting of the Invitation to Bid to newspapers of general circulation.

Procurement of goods, infrastructure projects and consulting services, where the amount involved does not exceed the threshold prescribed in Annex "H" of the revised Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR): Provided, that in case of Goods, the procurement does not fall under shopping in Section 52 of IRR (Official Gazette, 2018).

Problem 3: What are the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses in terms of procurement practices in utilization and the procurement processes?

Table 10 below presents the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses in terms of procurement practices in utilization. The result showed that with a mean of 3.61, the respondents go on “Shopping” as their mode of procurement followed by a mean of 2.23 Competitive Bidding, 2.26 Negotiated Procurement, 1.76 Limited Source Bidding or Selective Bidding, 1.89 Agency to Agency and 2.27 Repeat Order.

Table 10. Respondents’ Practices in the Utilization of the MOOE in terms of Procurement Practices in Utilization

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Shopping	3.61	±	0.51	Always
2. Competitive Bidding	2.23	±	0.95	Sometimes
3. Negotiated Procurement	2.26	±	0.85	Sometimes
4. Small Value Procurement	2.64	±	0.71	Often
5. Limited Source Bidding or Selective Bidding	1.76	±	0.78	Sometimes
6. Agency to Agency	1.89	±	1.14	Sometimes
7. Repeat Order	2.27	±	1.03	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.38	±	0.36	Sometimes

Note: 3.25-4.00 - Always; 2.50-3.24 - Often; 1.75-2.49 - Sometimes; 1.00-1.74 - Never

This study implied that the respondents' practices in the utilization of the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) is interpreted as 'sometimes' that is done to all procurement mode of utilization it is because there were certain guidelines that prohibits the school in acquiring such goods and services. RA 9184 stipulates the different requirements in obtaining and availing such goods and services needed by the school. Alternative Methods are subject to the prior approval of the Head of the Procuring Entity or his duly authorized representative, and whenever justified by the conditions provided in this Act, the Procuring Entity may, in order to promote economy and efficiency, resort to any of the following alternative methods of Procurement which are limited source Bidding, direct contracting, repeat order, shopping and negotiated procurement (GPPB, 2009).

This study further implies that Competitive Bidding, Negotiated Procurement, Limited Source Bidding or Selective Bidding was being done "sometimes" by the respondents because the attachments needed in the preparation of the required documents is crucial. It takes a lot of time in processing a document for approval on a certain project compared to Shopping and Small Value Procurement. While Agency to Agency pertains to utilities expense like water and electricity expenses by which schools were mostly on hinterlands. In addition, Repeat Order was also being done "sometimes" due to the mandate that it is not allowable to purchase a certain supplier repeatedly just only for the case supported by BAC Resolution saying the immediate need of the project and it is customary.

Table 11. *Practices in the Utilization of the MOOE in terms of Procurement Processes*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Identifying the needs of the school.	2.57	+	1.18	Practiced
2. Checking the legitimacy of the prospective suppliers.	3.07	+	0.90	Practiced
3. Sending of Request for Quotation (RFQ) at least 3 suppliers.	2.92	+	0.85	Practiced
4. Compare and obtain reasonable market pricing.	2.93	+	1.04	Practiced
5. Confirmation of supplier's data, terms of payment and delivery date.	2.92	+	0.99	Practiced
6. Preparation of check payment by Disbursing Officer	2.92	+	1.03	Practiced
7. Inspection of the released goods or services by the inspectorate team and School Property Custodian.	3.01	+	1.09	Practiced
8. BAC chairman notification on Commission on Audit officers for their inspection.	3.17	+	0.92	Practiced
9. Inventory of semi-expendable items purchased and issuance of Inventory Custodian Slip for Accountability.	3.15	+	0.97	Practiced
10. Release of materials to the recipient after it was recorded in Distribution List form (DL) and Requisition Issue Slip (RIS) for record-keeping.	3.10	+	1.11	Practiced
Weighted Mean	2.98	+	0.69	Practiced

Note: 3.25-4.00 – Highly Practiced; 2.50-3.24 - Practiced; 1.75-2.49 - Less Practiced; 1.00-1.74 - Not Practiced at All

Table 11 presents the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses in terms of procurement processes. The result showed that with a weighted mean of 2.98, respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes is being "practiced". The following steps are very important in availing as a mandate in procurement. No procurement shall be undertaken unless it is in accordance with the approved APP, including approved changes thereto. The APP must be consistent with the duly approved yearly budget of the Procuring Entity and shall bear the approval of the HoPE or second-ranking official designated by the HoPE to act on his behalf. (GPPB, 2009).

This further implies that the respondents' noted "practiced" means they are not well versed on the procurement processes on MOOE utilization because their learnings was limited to 2 to 5 trainings attended. It is not 'highly practiced" due to the fact that school varies its needs and undergo different mode of procurement. The expenditures of school budget will greatly depend on its priorities matching its Project Procurement Management Plan (PPMP) and/ or Approved Procurement Plan (APP) together with the Approved Quarterly School Operating Budget (SOB).

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile?

Table 12 displays the relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement practices in utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE had a highly significant relationship with their demographic profile in terms of civil status, educational attainment, and number of seminar/trainings attended. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and length of services were not rejected, while civil status, educational attainment, and number of seminar/training attended were rejected.

This study revealed that civil status, educational attainment, and seminars /trainings attended by the respondents give emphasis on the procurement practices on utilization. The maturity of a person helps them to be more aware and have a sense of responsibility in a wider and additional role. In addition, trainings were substantial for BAC members knowledgeable in procurement procedure. It is where a group meeting led by an expert that focuses on a specific topic or discipline. It has a numerous benefit, including improving communication skills, gaining expert knowledge, networking with others and renewing motivation and confidence.

With age, systematic declines are observed on cognitive tasks requiring self-initiated, effortful processing, without the aid of supportive memory cues. Older adults tend to perform poorer than young adults on memory tasks that involve recall of information, where individuals must retrieve information they learned previously without the help of a list of possible choices. For example, older adults

may have more difficulty recalling facts such as names or contextual details about where or when something happened. While research on interpersonal problem solving suggests that older adults use more effective strategies than younger adults to navigate through social and emotional problems (Blanchard-Fields, 2007). In the context of work, researchers rarely find that older individuals perform less well on the job (Park & Gutches, 2000). Similar to everyday problem solving, older workers may develop more efficient strategies and rely on expertise to compensate for cognitive decline. (Seattle, 2005)

Table 12. Relationship Respondents' Procurement Practices in Utilization and Demographic Profile

Variables	Procurement Practices in Utilization		Remarks	Decision
	X ² (df)	p-value		
Age	40.797 ^{ns} (48)	0.760	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Sex	14.624 ^{ns} (12)	0.263	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Civil status	25.481 ^{**} (12)	0.013	Significant	Reject H ₀
Educational attainment	75.762 ^{ns} (36)	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Length of service	36.126 ^{ns} (48)	0.896	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Number of seminar/training attended	97.167 ^{***} (36)	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Table 13 displays the relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes and the demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' procurement processes had no significant relationship with their demographic profile. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' procurement processes and the demographic profile was not rejected.

The study revealed that age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service and the number of seminars/ trainings attended is not significant as to procurement process.

Table 13. Relationship Respondents' Procurement Processes and Demographic Profile

Variables	Procurement Processes		Remarks	Decision
	X ² (df)	p-value		
Age	74.527 ^{ns} (96)	0.949	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Sex	15.997 ^{ns} (24)	0.880	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Civil status	16.641 ^{ns} (24)	0.864	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Educational attainment	41.966 ^{ns} (72)	0.998	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Length of service	97.268 ^{ns} (96)	0.445	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Number of seminar/training attended	78.551 ^{ns} (72)	0.279	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the level of awareness in procurement process?

Table 14. Relationship Respondents' Procurement Practices in Utilization and Level of Awareness

Variables	Procurement Practices in Utilization		Remarks	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
Level of awareness	0.406 ^{***}	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Pearson's r Correlation ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Table 14 displays the relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement practices in utilization and the level of awareness in procurement process. The result showed that the respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement practices in utilization had a highly significant relationship with the level of awareness in procurement process. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement practices in utilization and the level of awareness in procurement process was rejected.

This study implies that relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the level of awareness in procurement process revealed “significant”. Regulations are usually designed, first and foremost, to ensure transparency and reduce the potential for corruption but level of awareness among BAC members deemed on procurement practices because of the limited knowledge in procurement guidelines.

The study further implies that procurement processes was standard as stipulated in the procurement acts governed by Department of Budget Management (DBM), Commission on Audit (COA) and Dep Ed Orders. With this, respondents noted “significant” and that there is a need to know more on procurement acts and procedure as evidenced in Table 10 and Table 11.

Table 15 displays the relationship between the practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes and the level

of awareness in procurement process. The result showed that the respondents’ practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes had no significant relationship with the level of awareness in procurement process. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes and the level of awareness in procurement process was not rejected.

Table 15. Relationship Respondents’ Procurement Processes and Level of Awareness

Variables	Procurement Processes		Remarks	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
Level of awareness	0.102 ^{ns}	0.306	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0

Note: 1 – based on Pearson’s r Correlation ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

This study implies that procurement processes in relationship to level of awareness of the respondents has no significant and that the procurement process are stipulated in the Government Procurement Reform Act otherwise known as RA 9184.

Problem 6: Which of the demographic profile and level of awareness best predicts practices in the utilization of the MOOE of the respondents?

Table 16 presents the variables that best predict respondents’ procurement practices in utilization. The respondents’ procurement practices in utilization were affected by level of awareness with $\beta = 0.232$, $t = 2.964$, ($p < 0.004$). This implied that level of awareness was the only predictor that affects the respondents' procurement practices in utilization.

Table 16. Variables that best predict Respondents’ Procurement Practices in Utilization

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant)	1.756	0.410		4.286	.000
Age	0.022	0.044	0.056	0.498	0.619
Sex	-0.027	0.096	-0.026	-0.282	0.779
Civil status	-0.145	0.103	-0.141	-1.407	0.163
Educational attainment	0.091	0.068	0.130	1.331	0.186
Length of service	-0.029	0.031	-0.103	-0.948	0.346
Number of seminars attended	0.074	0.047	0.154	1.579	0.118
Level of awareness	0.232	0.078	0.308	2.964	0.004
R = 0.467		R ² = 0.218	F = 3.742	Sig. = 0.001	

The R2 value of 0.218 implies that 21.8% of the variance in procurement practices in utilization can be explained by the level of awareness. Hence, 78.2% of the respondents’ procurement practices in utilization difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. The regression analysis is significant, with an F-value of 3.742 with a corresponding p-value of 0.001. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents’ procurement practices in utilization” was rejected.

The study revealed that respondents’ procurement practices in utilization was affected by level of awareness and that more they acquire knowledge on MOOE utilization based on the stipulated guidelines in procurement Acts the less they encountered problems in submitting liquidation reports.

Table 17 presents the variables that best predict respondents’ procurement processes. The respondents’ procurement processes were not affected by the level of awareness. This implied that no variables in demographic profile and level of awareness that affect the respondents' procurement process.

Table 17. Variables that best predict Respondents’ Procurement Processes

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.050	0.868		3.514	0.001
Age	0.053	0.092	0.072	0.578	0.565
Sex	-0.128	0.204	-0.064	-0.625	0.533
Civil status	-0.222	0.218	-0.112	-1.018	0.311
Educational attainment	0.032	0.145	0.024	0.223	0.824
Length of service	0.006	0.066	0.011	0.095	0.925
Number of seminars attended	0.181	0.100	0.194	1.817	0.072
Level of awareness	0.031	0.166	0.021	0.185	0.854
R = 0.247		R ² = 0.061	F = 0.871	Sig. = 0.532	

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.871 with a corresponding p-value of 0.532. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents’ procurement processes” was not rejected.

The study revealed that respondents' procurement processes in utilization was not affected by its demographic profile and its level of awareness. The procurement acts served as a mandate that must be followed by the certain agency. The procurement processes were standard and the respondents were able to follow it.

Problem 7: What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

The department would benefit from creating a financial workshop among BAC members to ensure accurateness in the procurement process. This strategy would increase the teacher's degree of self-awareness so that they are totally equipped with knowledge the in preparation of liquidation reports. The action plan should also be thoroughly examined, carried out and documented so that the implementers will never take it lightly.

This action plan is designed to cater the technical aspects in preparing financial reports on Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) of school.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Most of the respondents were 33 to 41 years old, female, married, with a bachelor's degree, had rendered services for 2 – 5 years, and had attended less than two seminars/ trainings organized by the Department of Education and other accredited agencies.

In the respondents' level of awareness in terms of MOOE procurement process. The result showed with a mean of 3.45, the respondents were "very aware" in the procurement process that started with the preparation of the Annual Procurement Plan (APP) and PPMP as basis for procurement, preparation of the bidding documents by the BAC Secretariat, the issuance of the BAC Resolution Recommending the Award of the Contract with the bidder with the Lowest calculated responsive Bid, the Issuance of Notice to Award, signing of Contract or Purchase Order and the Issuance of Notice to proceed.

In terms of the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses as to the procurement practices in utilization. The result showed that with a mean of 3.61, the respondents go on "Shopping" as their mode of procurement. Likewise, the practices of the respondents in the utilization of the maintenance and other operating expenses in terms of procurement processes. The result showed that with a weighted mean of 2.98, respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement processes is being "practiced". The following steps are very important in availing as a mandate in procurement. No procurement shall be undertaken unless it is in accordance with the approved APP, including approved changes thereto. The APP must be consistent with the duly approved yearly budget of the Procuring Entity and shall bear the approval of the HoPE or second-ranking official designated by the HoPE to act on his behalf. (GPPB, 2009).

Further, in correlation, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' practices in the utilization of the MOOE and the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and length of services, was not rejected. In contrast, civil status, educational attainment, and number of seminar/training attended were rejected. At the same time, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between practices in the utilization of the MOOE in terms of procurement practices in utilization and the level of awareness in the procurement process, was rejected. However, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' procurement processes and the demographic profile, was not rejected.

Furthermore, in regression analysis, the respondents' procurement practices in utilization were affected by the level of awareness with $\beta = 0.232$, $t = 2.964$, ($p < 0.004$). This implied that the level of awareness was the only predictor that affects the respondents' procurement practices in utilization. The null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' procurement practices in utilization", was rejected.

In light of the findings, as mentioned above and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

To the DepEd Accounting/School Admin may assign Bids and Awards Committee members (BAC), Technical Working Group (TWG) who are most experienced.

Bids and Awards Committee members (BAC) must undergo series of trainings and workshops to be totally equipped with knowledge in procurement procedure as stipulated in General Guidelines in procurement.

The Head of Procuring Entity or the School Principal may select experienced teacher and/or serving the institution for longer years because they are knowledgeable enough pertaining to the needs of the school.

The teachers who are members of the BAC may be given time allowance by reducing their number of teaching workloads to be able them to cope up with the desired specified deadlines.

A Division level version of this study may be conducted to identify other related factors affecting the level of awareness in the procurement acts.

Other future researchers are also encouraged to conduct similar studies to identify other related factors on procurement practices such

as attitudes of these BAC members; and

Researchers are also encouraged to conduct a qualitative study to determine other related factors associated in the level of awareness of BAC members with regards to procurements.

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